

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

CONTENT OF HEAVY METALS IN STATION AREAS OF SOME CITIES IN GEORGIA

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ABSTRACT

Research conducted to study the gross content of heavy metals in station soils of some cities of Georgia, in particular on the Borjomi-Tbilisi line, made it possible for the first time to obtain information about the degree of pollution of stations. Based on the data obtained, may be stated that the ecological situation of the studied station areas is unfavorable - the gross content of heavy metals to substantial degree exceeds the MPC.

Keywords: Heavy metals, soil, analysis, contamination, railway station.

Introduction

Protecting soils, waters, and plants from pollution is an important task, since any harmful compounds found in the environment, sooner or later entering the human body, can accumulate in tissues, and primarily in bones [1-4]. Heavy metals, coming from the soil into plants and transmitted through food chains, have a toxic effect on plants, animals and humans. They are common pollutants, the monitoring of which is mandatory in soils and substrates. But they are not only toxicants, but also natural microcomponents of soils, the content of which is determined by the mechanical and chemical composition of soil-forming rocks and the nature of soil formation processes. The main role in fixing metals in the soil is played by organic substances, clay minerals and hydroxides of iron and manganese. During the sorption of heavy metals by soil, they are immobilized and converted into non-toxic forms, some of which are included in the crystal lattice of aluminosilicates. For example, technogenic lead and copper are transformed in the soil into less mobile compounds, and Zn and Cd into more mobile compounds.

The main source of soil contamination with heavy metals is the combustion of fossil fuels. The ash of coal and oil contains almost all metals in a total concentration of up to 500 g. This is the essence of the aerial-technogenic nature of the entry of heavy elements into the soil.

Other ways of heavy metals entering the soil also play a significant role in the pollution of soils. For example, annually more than 250 thousand tons of lead per year are released onto the soil surface from the exhaust gases of automobile engines running on leaded gasoline [5-7]. Transport not only has a direct negative impact on human health and life due to the risk of accidents, but it also has a strong impact on the environment, and without a doubt, it is one of the main ways that pollutants enter the air, water and soil [8].

Emissions into the atmosphere only from railway repair enterprises in the form of dust settling on the soil (mainly metal oxides) amount to over 380 thousand

tons per year. Train brake pads, when worn out, also introduce another 200 thousand tons of metals per year into the soils near railways. Heavy metals also enter the soils of railway areas during transportation in open cars and transshipment of various ores, mineral fertilizers, abrasion of wires and rails, and during the combustion of liquid and solid fuels at stationary and mobile sources. Thus, there is a steady increase in the scale of soil contamination with heavy metals. At the same time, the accumulation of the most toxic metals in the soil - mercury, lead, cadmium - is especially dangerous.

The main role in fixing metals in the soil is played by organic matter, clay minerals and hydroxides of iron and manganese [9]. At first, metals are sorbed mainly non-specifically. Over time, the connection of heavy metals with the soil absorption complex (SAC) becomes stronger, which is expressed in a decrease in the content of water-soluble and loosely bound forms. When heavy metals interact with clay minerals, exchangeable and nonexchangeable forms arise [9]. Technogenic zinc exhibits a greater affinity for the mineral components of PPC than copper, lead and cadmium. In this regard, the clay fraction of soils is enriched in zinc and depleted in copper and lead compared to the entire soil mass.

In the lower soil horizons, the main role in fixing heavy metals belongs to the oxides and hydroxides of Fe, Mn and Al. As indicated above, copper, zinc, and lead are most firmly fixed and actively sorbed. In soils rich in iron, many heavy metals become immobile due to occlusion processes.

Mercury, lead, cadmium and some other heavy metals are well sorbed in the upper layers (several centimeters thick) of the humus-accumulative (humus) horizon of various types of loamy soils. Their migration along the profile and removal beyond the soil profile is insignificant. However, in soils of light composition, acidic and depleted in humus, the processes of migration of these elements intensify.

The composition and quantity of elements retained in the soil depend on the content and composition of

humus, acid-base and redox conditions, sorption capacity, and the intensity of biological absorption. Some heavy metals are firmly retained by these components and not only do not participate in migration along the soil profile, but also do not pose a danger to living organisms. Therefore, the negative environmental consequences of soil pollution are associated with mobile metal compounds.

Transport not only has a direct negative impact on human health and life due to the risk of accidents [7-10], but it also has a strong impact on the environment, and without a doubt, it is one of the main routes for the penetration of pollutants into air, water and soil [11-15].

Unfortunately, detailed studies of the ecological state of soils in relation to heavy metals, both right-of-way of railways and the territories of railway transport enterprises (locomotive and carriage depots, stations, railway and washing stations, passenger carriage preparation points, etc.) are limited our country has not yet been carried out.

In this work, a study of the content of heavy metals in the soil of the railway station strip in the Borjomi-Khashuri-Kareli section was carried out.

Experimental part

During the field research, 228 soil samples (in depth 5, 10, 15 and 20 cm) were selected from the 4 upper layers of the soil of the mentioned objects. Each soil sample was collected on the "envelope" basis from different points across the area. From each station area, we collected soil samples from three points at four different depths, to the right, left and middle of the track, i.e., a total of 36 samples.

Their primary processing and preparation, determination of containing heavy metals, elemental analysis were carried out according to generally accepted

methods, in particular, using atomic absorption spectrometry. This method makes it possible to determine with great accuracy about eighty elements at low concentrations. The pH of the soil, humus, and the amount of non-volatile oil products were determined for a separate station.

1. Sample preparation

Preservation and transportation of samples for laboratory analysis (preparation and filling of containers, storage of samples, filtering of samples, etc.) was carried out according to GOST 31861-2012.

Mechanical impurities, plant roots and stones were removed from the air-dried sample. After loosening and sieving through a sieve with a diameter of 1 mm, we quartered the sample. We took an average sample.

2. Determination of heavy metals

We transferred 1.0000 g of the sample into a porcelain crucible previously brought to constant weight and heated it in a muffle at 450-500°C for 1 hour. Then we cooled it in a desiccator, weighed it and calculated the amount of organic substances by the weight difference.

We transferred the samples from the crucibles to 100 cm³ refractory chemical beakers. We poured 30 ml of mixture 3HCl+1HNO₃, left for 15 minutes and then dried to a dry residue. We repeated this procedure for the second time. Then we poured 30 ml of 10% hydrochloric acid, boiled it and transferred it to 50 cm³ measuring flasks, filled to the brim with the same acid. The amount of heavy metals was determined on an atomic absorption spectrophotometer AAnalyst 200 by Perkin Elmer according to ISO 8288-1986.

Results and discussion

The results of study the heavy metals content in some railway stations of Georgia are given in table 1.

Table 1.

The average content of heavy metals in railway station, including all layers, mg/kg

Parameter	Cu	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Co
Content in fresh soil ¹	2-40	20-800	5-50	2-20	10-80	-
Geochemical background ²	8.62-74.38	649-1631	27.76-56.74	4.50-12.12	57.40-92.60	12.4
MPC	3.0	1500	4.0	32.0	23	5.0
Borjomi	245.82	4486.38	122.22	408.16	415.2	132.08
Khashuri	1279.44	2568.05	150.97	727.12	322.49	2109.02
Qareli	622.53	1968.22	88.47	568.81	736.54	214.4
Gori	1754.44	3317.49	99.58	487.48	1747.91	822.22
Kaspi	1775.83	471.66	54.58	204.16	377.08	85.58
Mckheta	424.44	252.77	85.55	366.55	343.33	105.44
Tbilisi	113.89	189.72	50.55	180.43	135.41	46.44

¹ -Data from [16]

² - Calculated according [17]

³ - Are given on the basis [18].

It must be mentioned that in Georgia, there are no approved standards for the values of Maximum Permissible Concentrations (MPC) for heavy metals in soils; therefore we use the data of [16-18].

The data obtained indicate that almost all station areas are heavily polluted with heavy metals, especially the Khashuri and Gori stations. The copper content is more than 30 times higher than the maximum permissible concentration, lead 24 and 16 times, zinc 3 and 17 times, respectively (fig.1, 2). The cadmium content

ranges from 5-10 mg/kg, which exceeds the MPC by 10-20 times (the MPC for cadmium in soil in gross form is 0.5 mg/kg). The level of Cu concentration in soil depends on the distance of nearby railway as trains release Cu into the environment as well.

Oddly enough, the least polluted of all the objects studied is the Tbilisi Central Station: the amount of copper is only 2 times, and the amount of lead is 6 times higher than the maximum permissible concentration;

the content of Mn, Ni and Co is less than the maximum permissible concentration (Fig. 3).

The results showed that the depth from which soil samples were taken has virtually no effect on the HM content at all stations (Fig. 1-3). Only at the Khashursky station is there a pattern of increasing Mn content with increasing profile.

Most likely, this indicates an increased natural presence of manganese in the soils of the Khashur region, rather than anthropogenic impact. For the Borjomi station, an inverse relationship is observed to a

slight extent (Fig. 1), which is apparently due to the anthropogenic factor. The manganese content generally exceeds the maximum permissible concentration for the Borjomi-Khashuri line by 1.5-3 times, and in the Kaspi-Tbilisi section it decreases by almost an order of magnitude. This once again indicates an increased natural content of manganese in the soils of the Borjomi-Khashuri direction. The results obtained are also confirmed by data on the geochemical background (see table).

Fig.1. The influence of the soil profile on the content of heavy metals at the Borjomi railway station

Fig. 2. The influence of the soil profile on the content of heavy metals at the Khashuri railway station

Fig. 3. The influence of the soil profile on the content of heavy metals at the Tbilisi Central Station

Fig.4. Distribution of heavy metals across the studied objects

The manganese content in the station soils of Borjomi, Khashuri, Kareli, and Gori is more than an order of magnitude higher than in the soils of the Kaspi, Mtskheta, and Tbilisi stations (Fig. 4). The amount of lead is approximately the same in all studied areas, although in a number of studies [19-22] is mentioned that under a negative anthropogenic effect, the mobility of metals can greatly alter and natural low-activity Pb can even become very mobile. The distribution of zinc and, to a greater extent, copper has uneven character.

According to the degree of pollution, the studied station areas are arranged in the following order: Khashuri>Gori>Kareli>Borjomi>Kaspi>Mtskheta>Tbilisi, and heavy metals form the following order: Mn>Cu>Zn>Pb>Co>Ni>Cd.

The composition and quantity of elements retained in the soil depend on the content and composition of humus, acid-base and redox conditions, sorption capacity, and the intensity of biological absorption [23].

Heavy metals in soils can be in the form of ions, various organic or mineral compounds, which have varying degrees of mobility and danger to living organisms. Redox conditions and environmental reactions dramatically change the behavior of heavy metals in the landscape. The migration ability of copper, nickel, cobalt, zinc in sharply reducing conditions decreases by 1-2 orders of magnitude compared to oxidizing conditions. Under oxidizing conditions in an acidic environment, copper, zinc, nickel, and lead are more mobile than in a neutral or alkaline environment. Since the pH of the environment for all samples fluctuated between 7-8, i.e., the environment was neutral or slightly alkaline, these metals are in a sedentary form and therefore pose less of a threat to the environment.

Ni, Cr, and Mn present in the contaminated soil, because these metals are components of the railway steel. Therefore, their source can be the abrasion of rails and wheels. The herbicides are goods of railway transport very often and contain Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn. But, to compare to the heavy metal content in the ballast stones, the herbicides can be considered a negligible source of these pollutants.

Conclusion

Thus, based on the data obtained, may be stated that the ecological situation of the studied station areas is unfavorable - with the exception of nickel, the gross content of heavy metals to substantial degree exceeds the MPC. It can be said that railway transport is a potential source of these heavy metals, especially at junction stations where railway freight trains stand idle for a long time or perform maneuvers. Such stations were Khashuri and Gori, the station lines of which were especially polluted. Over the 150 years of existence of the Transcaucasia Railway, a huge amount of pollutants have accumulated in the soil that was not dissolving by washing waters.

Research conducted to study the gross content of heavy metals in station soils of some cities of Georgia, in particular on the Borjomi-Tbilisi line, made it possible for the first time to obtain information about the degree of pollution of stations with heavy metals.

The authors of the article express deep gratitude to students of the chemistry department of Tbilisi State University G. Mimoshvili, D. Gabadadze, and M. Gabadadze for assistance in sample collection and analysis.

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